

Lanthanide Metal Chelates of Salicylaldehyde Phenylhydrazone

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Although metal complexes of hydrazones derived from hydrazides have been investigated in detail¹, those derived from hydrazines seem to have been neglected. In this investigation phenylhydrazones of *o*-hydroxyaraldehydes (latter type) have been found to have strong affinity for lanthanide ions. Complexes of salicylaldehyde phenylhydrazone (Hsph) with the entire series of available lanthanides are reported herein.

Results and Discussion

Analytical data (Table 1) of Ln^{III} complexes indicated² a general formula, [Ln(sph)(OH)₂(OH₂)₂]. Under the experimental condition, cerium(III) salts were found to be oxidised even by atmospheric air. Cerium(IV) complex was however obtained pure starting from cerium(IV) ammonium nitrate.

Like the cerium(IV) complex, the terbium complex also liberated one equivalent of iodine from KI in acetic acid medium, and the observed magnetic moment of the latter is almost identical to that of Gd^{III}, which has also the *f*⁷ electronic configuration. Subject to further confirmation, this is the first instance of isolation of a terbium(IV) complex. Conductance measurements showed that the cerium complex is a 1 : 1 electrolyte and that the others are non-electrolytes.

Lanthanide ions exist as aqua-complexes in aqueous medium, and in presence of chelating agents which effect partial substitution, precipitation of mixed hydroxo complexes occurs³ at characteristic pHs (Table 1). Thermal studies of the complexes indicated weight-loss for two water molecules eliminated in the temperature range 150–220°.

The visible spectral bands (*f-f* bands) of lanthanides are hypersensitive to stereochemistry⁴. Since

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF LANTHANIDE METAL COMPLEXES OF HSPH

Compd.	Colour	pH at precipitation	Analytical data %: Found (Calcd.)*				Magnetic moment B.M.	Conductance Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹
			Metal	C	H	N		
[La(sph)(OH) ₂ (OH ₂) ₂]	Pale brown	7.20	32.68 (33.07)	37.02 (37.15)	4.24 (4.05)	6.58 (6.66)	Diamag.	3.48
[Pr(sph)(OH) ₂ (OH ₂) ₂]	Pale brown	7.91	33.48 (33.40)	36.68 (36.97)	4.18 (4.03)	6.53 (6.64)	3.29	3.16
[Nd(sph)(OH) ₂ (OH ₂) ₂]	Brown	7.84	33.43 (33.92)	36.37 (36.69)	4.02 (4.00)	6.54 (6.58)	3.25	2.11
[Sm(sph)(OH) ₂ (OH ₂) ₂]	Pale green	7.81	34.63 (34.86)	36.14 (36.17)	3.89 (3.94)	6.52 (6.49)	2.04	2.32
[Eu(sph)(OH) ₂ (OH ₂) ₂]	Pale brown	8.34	35.32 (35.10)	36.11 (36.03)	3.96 (3.93)	6.58 (6.47)	3.79	2.08
[Gd(sph)(OH) ₂ (OH ₂) ₂]	Pale brown	7.54	35.46 (35.88)	35.72 (35.60)	3.91 (3.88)	6.49 (6.39)	7.81	3.84
[Dy(sph)(OH) ₂ (OH ₂) ₂]	Pale yellow	8.77	36.64 (36.64)	35.21 (35.17)	3.78 (3.83)	6.48 (6.31)	9.68	3.98
[Ho(sph)(OH) ₂ (OH ₂) ₂]	Pale yellow brown	7.60	36.08 (36.99)	34.24 (34.98)	3.64 (3.81)	6.71 (6.28)	9.71	2.04
[Er(sph)(OH) ₂ (OH ₂) ₂]	Brown	7.95	37.84 (37.31)	34.11 (34.80)	3.16 (3.79)	6.22 (6.25)	9.21	2.94
[Tm(sph)(OH) ₂ (OH ₂) ₂]	Pale yellow	8.51	37.12 (37.55)	34.22 (34.67)	3.18 (3.78)	6.48 (6.22)	7.08	4.11
[Yb(sph)(OH) ₂ (OH ₂) ₂]	Pale yellowish brown	8.21	38.96 (38.11)	34.53 (34.36)	3.28 (3.74)	6.47 (6.17)	4.21	3.91
[Lu(sph)(OH) ₂ (OH ₂) ₂]	Pale yellow	7.32	38.37 (38.37)	34.88 (34.21)	3.96 (3.73)	6.43 (6.14)	Diamag.	4.21
[Ce(sph) ₂ (NO ₃)(OH ₂) ₂]NO ₃	Brown	5.00	19.82 (19.40)	43.36 (43.20)	3.91 (3.60)	11.71 (11.63)	Diamag.	83.24
[Tb(sph) ₂ (OH) ₂ (OH ₂) ₂]	Pale brown	6.01	24.42 (24.19)	48.08 (47.94)	4.38 (4.30)	8.79 (8.60)	7.84	3.11

*Metal content by standard procedures and C, H and N microanalytically; hydrazone moiety was estimated⁷ also using ICl.

NOTES

the effect is most pronounced for Nd^{III}, spectrum of its complex was recorded in DMF. The simple two-peak feature observed (573, 588 nm) is characteristic of six-coordination⁴. Nujol mull spectrum (peaks at ~ 570 and 580 nm) was similar, though broader, suggesting that the stereochemistry is the same in the solid state also. By analogy, the same structure is presumed for all the lanthanide complexes.

Bonding mode of the ligand has been judged through comparison of its ir spectrum with those of the complexes. The observed depression of $\nu_{C=N}$ and heightening of $\nu_{C=O}$ (by 10 and 40 cm^{-1} respectively) indicate chelation through azomethine nitrogen and phenolate oxygen⁶. The non-ligand bands at 485–450 and 350–330 cm^{-1} in the spectra of all the complexes are presumably due to ν_{M-O} and ν_{M-N} respectively⁶. Spectrum revealed that nitrate acts as bidentate in the cerium complex. Formula of a chloro-complex prepared similarly, $[\text{Ce}(\text{sph})_2\text{Cl}_2(\text{OH})_2]$, supports the bidentate nature of nitrate.

Experimental

Rare earths used were either Specpure oxides from Johnson Matthey or coded oxides from Lindsay Chemical. Hitachi U 3400 uv spectrophotometer, Perkin-Elmer 599 ir spectrophotometer, Uvac Sinku-Riku T.A. 1500 differential thermomicrobalance, Global DPH 500 pH meter, Toshniwal conductivity bridge, and Cahn-Faraday electrobalance were used.

General method of preparation of Ln^{III} complexes: Pure Ln₂O₃ was dissolved in 1 : 1 nitric acid by heating. An aliquot of this solution containing 60 mg of Ln was diluted to about 10 ml with distilled water and then added slowly to a slight excess of Hsph (1 : 1 molar ratio) in ethanol (~ 30 ml). The mixture was stirred, pH adjusted to the value shown in Table 1 with 1M ammonia and the stirring continued for 15–20 min. The complex formed was washed successively with water, 50% ethanol and ethanol and dried at 90°.

For preparing the terbium complex, 1 : 2 metal-hydrazone ratio was necessary.

Preparation of Ce^{IV} complex: Cerium(IV) ammonium nitrate (A.R. ; ~ 1 g) was dissolved in 50% ethanol (~ 15 ml). An aliquot of this solution containing 60 mg of Ce^{IV} was added slowly to a solution of Hsph (Ce : Hsph = 1 : 2) in ethanol (~ 50 ml). The crystals formed were filtered after stirring for 5 min, washed successively with water, 50% ethanol and ethanol and dried at 90°.

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